

Evaluation of the effect of live haulage on metabolites and fillet texture of rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*)

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Abstract

Changes in metabolites and meat texture of pan-sized live rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*), were examined following commercial, international road haulage. Significant ($P < 0.001$) increases in water, NH_4^+ and pH were detected during haulage. Transportation decreased ($P < 0.05$) dark muscle glycogen and L-tactate. Textural parameters, including hardness, elasticity, and breakpoint of the raw fillet, were unaffected by the haulage process. Muscle pH increased ($P < 0.05$) both in fish exposed to starvation and transportation when compared to reference fish. The results obtained indicate that haulage has limited effects upon fish flesh quality.